

The Functioning of Phraseological Intensifiers in Different Types of Discourse

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Abstract: *The article attempts to consider the phraseological means of expressing intensification in the modern English language. As a result of the study, the author reveals the structures of phraseological units that convey the expressive meaning of a high degree of any feature or action. The semantic and structural characteristics of the studied phraseological units are presented. The paper ascertains that comparative phraseological units are the most frequent ones among other phraseological means of expressing intensification in the modern English language. The analysis shows that the components of some phraseological units may emerge eventually from a fixed phraseological unit and become such means of intensification that can be combined with a number of units of both similar and diverse semantics.*

Keywords: *phraseology, intensifiers, intensity, expansiveness, deceitfulness, monotonous, discourse, household.*

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Introduction. Intensification in Phraseology for the first time the question concerning intensification in phraseology was risen in Logan P. Smith's work "English Idioms", which was published in the books "Society for pure English" in 1922 and became a part of the book "Words and Idioms. Studies in the English language" in 1925. In the given work we find the first mention about PI with intensification meaning. The PHI could be considered from their origin, their structural-semantic and grammatical characteristics, modes of appearance, peculiarities of their use in modern English. The PHI which expresses strong feelings facing expressive redefining and in most cases their components lose their literal meaning which results in PU with total intensification meaning (Kunin 1972). The peculiarity of the reflection of the category of intensity in the phraseological level of the language is based on the features of the categorical properties of phraseological units, as well as on the specifics of their semantics. If the interaction of emotive and evaluative sem occurs in the composition of the connotative macroelement of the phraseological unit with the intensity element, it provides a greater speech effect of phraseological units in comparison with the corresponding lexemes and combinations. The PHI could contribute a lot to emphasizing urgent problems and to achieving politician's and journalist's communicative intention to influence the audience. Political figures may influence the emotional sphere of the potential elector's personality with the help of the PHI.

Discussions and results. The final section is presented by an analysis of the discourse of the linguistic personality of Holden Caulfield, the main character of J. D. Salinger's novel "The Catcher in the Rye". The introduction of the concept of personality into discourse means the opportunity to

say that a person is aware of his attitude to the accepted principles and conventions of conducting discourse and creatively uses them in his speech actions. Personality in discourse merges with the concept of linguistic personality in the most general, global, socio-psychological sense, since, according to the definition of Y.N.Karaulov, "linguistic personality is the deepening, development, saturation with additional content of personality in general"

Understanding by the discourse of personality, following Y.N.Karaulov, the entire process of speaking and the result of this process recorded over a relatively long period of time (Karaulov 1988), we offer as an example of such a discourse the entire set of texts generated by Holden Caulfield. It was not by chance that we chose the discourse of this particular linguistic personality for analysis. In the discourse of this sixteen-year-old teenager, it was possible to identify a whole cascade of PHI (about 88 uses). For what purpose does this linguistic personality use such a number of PHI in his speech? We will try to answer this question by systematizing the totality of statements made in the external and internal speech of this character. Statements containing PHI, since, according to Z.A.Kuznetsevich, spiritual life is objectified in a person's speech actions, his linguistic behavior, i.e. in a broad sense in the texts generated by him (Kuznetsevich 1999). Here we can talk about clarifying the well-known thesis of F.de Saussure says that behind every text there is a language system. Y.N.Karaulov suggests a different interpretation of this well-known postulate: "behind each text there is a creatively developed linguistic personality," in the structure of which the scientist identifies three levels:

- 1) verbal-semantic or lexicon;
- 2) linguistic-cognitive or thesaurus;
- 3) motivational or pragmatics (Karaulov 1987).

Considering speech activity, first of all, as the creative activity of Holden Caulfield's linguistic personality, we will begin with the motivational level reflecting the pragmatics of personality, i.e. the system of its goals, motives, attitudes and intentionalities that drive the development of a linguistic personality, its behavior, as well as controlling the text production of personality. To express his attitudes, intentions towards another person, towards the world, towards being in general, Holden Caulfield turns to a certain type of discourse, namely narrative. However, Holden often has to defend his point of view, his life position, and his view of society in front of the interlocutor, so there are elements of argumentation in his discourse. Thus, Holden Caulfield's discourse can be characterized as narratively argumentative, which in turn is presented in two types - external and internalized speech. The interiorization of speech actions is an important characteristic of a linguistic personality. The abundance of interiorized speech in the hero's discourse can qualify him as a person leading a rich inner life, saturated with emotional and intellectual experiences (Kuznetsevich 1999). The main form in which Holden's internalized speech is presented is an internal monologue. It is in him that the spiritual and moral character of a teenager is revealed. It should be noted that personality is most often and most easily revealed in inner speech. According to Z.A.Kuznetsevich, a person is most open with himself, because the inner world is practically inaccessible to observation in external speech (Kuznetsevich 1999). Thus, it can be considered that Holden Caulfield's inner speech provides access to his inner world, to his intentional horizon, which is determined by the intentional state associated with the teenager's heightened reaction to "fake" or "fake", to the discrepancy between the real and the apparent. This is evidenced by the fact that the word phony (fake, linden) is one of the key words in Holden's lexicon, and the key word is the exponent of the intentional horizon. Such a transition of a keyword from the lexicon to pragmatics is a clear example of the mutual penetration of levels in the structure of a linguistic personality, as Y.N.Karaulov wrote (Karaulov 1987).

The presence of assessments and self-assessments in Holden Caulfield's discourse is a way of his self-affirmation, substantiation of his life positions, ideals, values. As the linguistic material shows, the emotional and evaluative statements of the addressee about himself prevail in the hero's discourse, i.e. egocentric statements, which, according to L.P.Chakhoyan's classification, can be descriptive and relational (Chakhoyan 1990). Holden's discourse presents mainly descriptive egocentric statements with PHI, which are descriptions of physical behavior, for example: "Then I took out my door key and quietly, like hell, opened our door" (J.D. Salinger "The Catcher in the Rye", p. 142), "Quietly, like hell, I entered D.B.'s room and turned on the lamp on the table" (decre. op., p. 143), "I just put a notebook and pencil in my pocket and rushed to her school as fast as I could" (decree.soc., p. 179), etc., description of speech and intellectual activity, example: "I said it damn politely" (Ukraine. Op., pp. 57, 85)," I said. Damn cold" (p. 36), "I'm not saying it ruined our conversation, but damn, nothing good came of it" (p.101), "I think it's because she was damn young" (p.85), "I know old Ackley it was damn annoying" (p. 19), etc., also a description of public opinion, among which we were, there were highlighted statements verbalizing the collective state, example: "I also damn much wanted to see it" (p. 106), "I just felt damn sad" (p. 138), "I was fucking embarrassed" (p. 172), "I was fucking excited thinking about it" (p. 179) and emotional states, for example: "I felt damn sorry for him" (p. 12), "I felt damn sad..." (p. 12, 86), "I was damn depressed..." (p. 135), etc..

"Intensity is a measure of the expansiveness of the speaker's personality, it is an indicator of his speech temperament." As shown by the analysis of the pragmicon of Holden's discourse, the character is very active, one might even say, very violently and directly manifests his emotional experiences, affects others, which in turn indicates that Holden Caulfield is an emotional linguistic personality in speech activity. At the same time, the dominant states in his discourse are intentional states of regret, despondency and sadness. A red thread through the entire discourse of Holden Caulfield runs an intentional state of hatred towards a society that lives in a fog of false concepts generated by himself about its meaning and role in the modern world. Pursuing the most base, unspiritual goals, society asserts its fictional, idyllic image in theater and cinema. Holden hates the "deceitfulness" of cinema and theater, which the public is so greedy for. The intentional state of hatred directed at theater and cinema is evidenced by the following two fragments of narrative discourse, which are sequences of assertive speech acts, which, according to T. van Dyck's method of discursive analysis, impart personality as a subject of discourse (van Dyck 1989).

Conclusion. Summarizing the above, it should be emphasized that in modern English there is a relatively large number of different-structured phraseological units that convey the expressive meaning of a high degree of any sign or action, namely: comparative phraseological units, prepositional-substantive phraseological units, paired combinations of words and phraseological constructions, which are characterized by a free lexical replacement of the core component or are implemented for the account of verbs, which by their meaning hyperbolize the described phenomena, which do not actually occur. The most common of these are comparative phraseological units.

The analyzed stable combinations express a quantitative meaning and give the statement imagery and emotionality. The components of some phraseological units may eventually break out of the close phraseological environment and begin to function as intensifiers, combining with a number of units of monotonous or diverse semantics.

In the role of the core components of the considered phraseological units, either words are used that name concepts that have a certain feature to a greater extent, or words indicating by their meaning that they go beyond the usual, generally accepted.

Such phraseological units are the most effective means of enhancing the effectiveness of what is being stated. Their primary sphere of use is colloquial and household.

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